

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGO NGOA****FIRST NAME: HERMINE GERALDE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What endeavor is achieved by an academic essay?

- An academic essay presents arguments about a topic with specific examples through critical thinking.
- An essay analyzes and writes about the findings of a research topic.
- An academic essay aims to answer hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.¹**
- An academic essay demonstrates a particular understanding of a topic and the ability to adhere to specific writing conventions.

2. Writing a research paper or an academic dissertation is a meticulous process that involves:

- Prewriting to make sure you understand your assignment, Research, and Drafting. Write and revise to make it Better, then edit and proofread to correct it.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

- Research the topic, organize your ideas, write the essay, reference the essay, edit, and hand or present the essay.²**
 - Choose an Essay topic, conduct research, create an outline, write the introduction, body, and conclusion, and revise and edit your essay.
 - Analyzing the topic/question, conducting research, brainstorming, outlining, formulating a thesis, writing, revising, and finally proofreading,
3. Every research is unique, but the process and steps are the same. What are the processes and habits of the mind that underlie research?
- Explore, test, and systematically generate answers to a problem.
 - Discover, understand, and develop new theories about an issue.
 - Collect information, inquire, test, and provide an answer to a specific question.³**
 - Acquire information and develop some knowledge that can be useful to solve problems.
4. Every research paper is unique in structure and depth. Why is a specific citation style required?
- Because citation styles evolve as technology and the types of resources used in research change to meet the needs of particular disciplines.
 - Using the correct citation style is essential for academic integrity, avoiding plagiarism, and allowing readers to locate sources easily.
 - Readers expect you to use citation styles appropriate to their field to show you understand their values and practices.⁴**

² Ibid., 7-10.

³ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago : The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 18-21.

⁴ Ibid., 140.

- Because different fields have unique needs, for example, the humanities might prioritize page numbers for easy location of specific passages. At the same time, the sciences might emphasize the publication date to track the evolution of knowledge.
5. Writing an academic paper requires two crucial parts: the content and the form. The form is the vehicle of the form. How do you make sure this vehicle is well-designed?
- The way a writer forms and arranges the sentences, uses language, and word choice to create a specific meaning and tone to the text.
 - Focus on word choice, sentence structure, and text organization in a narrative, descriptive, expository, or persuasive way.
 - Using proper orthography, a writing system encompasses spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and word breaks. Using grammar style consists of the optional word choice and sentence structure that influences the overall tone and impact of writing.⁵**
 - Refers to the structure and organization of the text, including the genre, type, and purpose of the writing.
6. What are the key elements of choosing a research method?
- Quantitative research involves measuring or counting something and expressing the result numerically. In contrast, qualitative research involves describing something in non-numerical terms, such as its appearance, texture, or color.
 - Qualitative research is valuable for studies at the individual level and for finding out, in depth, how people think or feel. Quantitative research gathers data in numerical form, which can be put into categories, in rank order, or measured in units of measurement.
 - Analyzing quantitative data is easier and requires less effort than analyzing qualitative data. Answers are turned into numbers and statistics that you can use to fuel your business strategy.

⁵ Ibid., 36-44.

- The most important element is the research question. This question will stimulate hypotheses and guide the choice of the method that will be used for the research to examine all aspects of the topic.**⁶
7. What is the importance of a citation connector like Zotero in writing a dissertation?
- Students at Euclid University are advised to use Zotero, a citation tool that you can use to connect to Microsoft Word to add/edit citations and bibliography. Be sure to select Turabian 8th edition as the citation style. Even then, changes may need to be made.**⁷
- Citation tools are source reference management software that manage bibliographic data and related research materials, such as PDF and ePUB files. Features include web browser integration, online syncing, generation of in-text citations, footnotes, and bibliographies, integrated PDF, ePUB, and HTML readers with annotation capabilities, and a note editor.
- A reference management tool helps researchers collect, organize, cite, and share research sources, including books, articles, and other materials, and create bibliographies.
- A citation like Zotero helps you build a bibliography instantly from any computer or device, without creating an account or installing any software.
8. Besides developing good research habits, good time management, and taking responsibility for your learning, what else could help you avoid plagiarism?
- Practice effective quoting, paraphrasing, and summarizing. Use quotation marks and cite the source.
- Use Grammarly, an English language writing assistant software tool that reviews the spelling, grammar, and tone of a piece of writing. It can also identify possible instances of plagiarism and suggest style and tonal recommendations to users through writing from prompts.**⁸
- Ensure everything you type is accurate in spelling, punctuation, and grammar, clear, compelling, and easy to read.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 28-35.

⁷ Euclid University

⁸ Ibid.

- Eliminate wordiness, improve sentence structure, and use active voice, making your writing clearer and easier to understand.

9. Why would the European Union need specific written English style guidelines?

- Because English is a widely spoken language globally, it makes it a practical choice for international communication and business.
- English is a common language understood by most of the European population.
- Some people say that English is a neutral language and using it will avoid potential language-based tensions within the EU.
- European Union-specific written English style seeks to facilitate and encourage writing clear and reader-friendly English in such a complex environment.⁹**

10. To what extent did the context of the Cold War impact the history of Europe?

- The Cold War divided Europe physically and ideologically, with the Iron Curtain separating Western, capitalist countries from Eastern, communist countries.
- The formation of NATO and the Warsaw Pact solidified the division of Europe and led to a massive arms race, with both sides building up their military strength.
- The experiences of the Cold War have influenced the development of European integration and the growth of the European Union to foster economic cooperation and prevent future conflicts in Europe.¹⁰**
- The Treaty of Maastricht (1992) officially established the European Union and set the stage for a single currency (the euro) and closer cooperation in foreign and security policy.

⁹ European Commission, *European Commission English Style Guide*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 1.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 60-64.

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